

STRESS AND HEALTH: PSYCHOLOGICAL, BEHAVIORAL, AND BIOLOGICAL DETERMINANTS

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Abstract: Stressors have a major influence upon mood, our sense of well-being, behavior, and health. Acute stress responses in young, healthy individuals may be adaptive and typically do not impose a health burden. However, if the threat is unremitting, particularly in older or unhealthy individuals, the longterm effects of stressors can damage health. The relationship between psychosocial stressors and disease is affected by the nature, number, and persistence of the stressors as well as by the individual's biological vulnerability (i.e., genetics, constitutional factors), psychosocial resources, and learned patterns of coping. Psychosocial interventions have proven useful for treating stress-related disorders and may influence the course of chronic diseases.

Keywords: psychosocial stressors; stress responses; homeostasis; psychosocial interventions; host vulnerability stressor interactions

INTRODUCTION

Claude Bernard (1865/1961) noted that the maintenance of life is critically dependent on keeping our internal milieu constant in the face of a changing environment. Cannon (1929) called this "homeostasis." Selye (1956) used the term "stress" to represent the effects of anything that seriously threatens homeostasis. The actual or perceived threat to an organism is referred to as the "stressor" and the response to the stressor is called the "stress response."

Although stress responses evolved as adaptive processes, Selye observed that severe, prolonged stress responses might lead to tissue damage and disease. Based on the appraisal of perceived threat, humans and other animals invoke coping

responses (Lazarus & Folkman 1984). Our central nervous system (CNS) tends to produce integrated coping responses rather than single, isolated response changes (Hilton 1975). Thus, when immediate fight-or-flight appears feasible, mammals tend to show increased autonomic and hormonal activities that maximize the possibilities for muscular exertion (Cannon 1929, Hess1957).. However, if the threat is persistent, particularly in older or unhealthy individuals, the long-term effects of the response to stress may damage health (Schneiderman 1983). Adverse effects of chronic stressors are particularly common in humans, possibly because their high capacity for symbolic thought may elicit persistent stress responses to a broad range of adverse living and working conditions. The relationship between psychosocial stressors and chronic disease is complex. It is affected, for example, by the nature, number, and persistence of the stressors as well as by the individual's biological vulnerability (i.e., genetics, constitutional factors) and learned patterns of coping.

In this review, we focus on some of the psychological, behavioral, and biological effects of specific stressors, the mediating psychophysiological pathways, and the variables known to mediate these relationships. We conclude with a consideration of treatment implications.

PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF STRESS

Stressors During Childhood and Adolescence and Their Psychological Sequelae

The most widely studied stressors in children and adolescents are exposure to violence, abuse (sexual, physical, emotional, or neglect), and divorce/marital conflict (see Cicchetti 2005). McMahon et al. (2003) also provide an excellent review of the psychological consequences of such stressors. Psychological effects of maltreatment/abuse include the dysregulation of affect, provocative behaviors, the avoidance of intimacy, and disturbances in attachment (Haviland et al. 1995, Lowenthal 1998). Survivors of childhood sexual abuse have higher levels of both

general distress and major psychological disturbances including personality disorders (Polusny & Follett 1995). Childhood abuse is also associated with negative views toward learning and poor school performance (Lowenthal 1998). Children of divorced parents have more reported antisocial behavior, anxiety, and depression than their peers (Short 2002). Adult offspring of divorced parents report more current life stress, family conflict, and lack of friend support compared with those whose parents did not divorce (Short 2002). Exposure to nonresponsive environments has also been described as a stressor leading to learned helplessness (Peterson & Seligman 1984)

Studies have also addressed the psychological consequences of exposure to war and terrorism during childhood (Shaw 2003). A majority of children exposed to war experience significant psychological morbidity, including both post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) and depressive symptoms. For example, Nader et al. (1993) found that 70% of Kuwaiti children reported mild to severe PTSD symptoms after the Gulf War. Some effects are long lasting: Macksound & Aber (1996) found that 43% of Lebanese children continued to manifest post-traumatic stress symptoms 10 years after exposure to war-related trauma. Exposure to intense and chronic stressors during the developmental years has long-lasting

neurobiological effects and puts one at increased risk for anxiety and mood disorders, aggressive dyscontrol problems, hypo-immune dysfunction, medical morbidity, structural changes in the CNS, and early death (Shaw 2003).

Stressors During Adulthood and Their Psychological Sequelae

LIFE STRESS, ANXIETY, AND DEPRESSION—It is well known that first depressive episodes often develop following the occurrence of a major negative life event (Paykel 2001). Furthermore, there is evidence that stressful life events are causal for the onset of depression (see Hammen 2005, Kendler et al. 1999). A study of 13,006 patients in Denmark, with first psychiatric admissions diagnosed with depression, found more recent divorces, unemployment, and

suicides by relatives compared with age- and gender-matched controls (Kessing et al. 2003). The diagnosis of a major medical illness often has been considered a severe life stressor and often is accompanied by high rates of depression (Cassem 1995). For example, a meta-analysis found that 24% of cancer patients are diagnosed with major depression (McDaniel et al. 1995). Stressful life events often precede anxiety disorders as well (Faravelli & Pallanti 1989, FinlayJones & Brown 1981). Interestingly, long-term follow-up studies have shown that anxiety occurs more commonly before depression (Angst & Vollrath 1991, Breslau et al. 1995). In fact, in prospective studies, patients with anxiety are most likely to develop major depression after stressful life events occur (Brown et al. 1986).

DISORDERS RELATED TO TRAUMA—Lifetime exposure to traumatic events in the general population is high, with estimates ranging from 40% to 70% (Norris 1992). Of note, to sexual assault (Kilpatrick et al. 1992). The Diagnostic and Statistical Manual (DSM-IV-TR; American

Psychiatric Association 2000) includes two primary diagnoses related to trauma: Acute Stress Disorder (ASD) and PTSD. Both these disorders have as prominent features a traumatic event involving actual or threatened death or serious injury and symptom clusters including reexperiencing of the traumatic event (e.g., intrusive thoughts), avoidance of reminders/numbing, and hyperarousal (e.g., difficulty falling or staying asleep). The time frame for ASD is shorter (lasting two days to four weeks), with diagnosis limited to within one month of the incident. ASD was introduced in 1994 to describe initial trauma reactions, but it has come under criticism (Harvey & Bryant 2002) for weak empirical and theoretical support. Most people who have symptoms of PTSD shortly after a traumatic event recover and do not develop PTSD. In a comprehensive review, Green (1994) estimates that approximately 25% of those exposed to traumatic events develop PTSD. Surveys of the general population indicate that PTSD affects 1 in 12 adults at some time in their life (Kessler et al. 1995). Trauma and disasters are related not

only to PTSD, but also to concurrent depression, other anxiety disorders, cognitive impairment, and substance abuse (David et al. 1996, Schnurr et al. 2002, Shalev 2001). Other consequences of stress that could provide linkages to health have been identified, such as increases in smoking, substance use, accidents, sleep problems, and eating disorders. Populations that live in more stressful environments (communities with higher divorce rates, business failures, natural disasters, etc.) smoke more heavily and experience higher mortality from lung cancer and chronic obstructive pulmonary disorder (Colby et al. 1994)

Variations in Stress Responses

Certain characteristics of a situation are associated with greater stress responses. These include the intensity or severity of the stressor and controllability of the stressor, as well as features that determine the nature of the cognitive responses or appraisals. Life event dimensions of loss, humiliation, and danger are related to the development of major depression and generalized anxiety (Kendler et al. 2003). Factors associated with the development of symptoms of PTSD and mental health disorders include injury, damage to property, loss of resources, bereavement, and perceived life threat (Freedy et al. 1992, Ironson et al. 1997, McNally 2003). Recovery from a stressor can also be affected by secondary traumatization (Pfefferbaum et al. 2003). Other studies have found that multiple facets of stress that may work synergistically are more potent than a single facet; for example, in the area of work stress, time pressure in combination with threat (Stanton et al. 2001), or high demand in combination with low control (Karasek & Theorell 1990).

PSYCHOSOCIAL STRESSORS AND HEALTH

Cardiovascular Disease

Both epidemiological and controlled studies have demonstrated relationships between psychosocial stressors and disease. The underlying mediators, however, are unclear in most cases, although possible mechanisms have been explored in

some experimental studies. An occupational gradient in coronary heart disease (CHD) risk has been documented in which men with relatively low socioeconomic status have the poorest health outcomes (Marmot 2003). Much of the risk gradient in CHD can be eliminated, however, by taking into account lack of perceived job control, which is a potent stressor (Marmot et al. 1997). Other factors include risky behaviors such as smoking, alcohol use, and sedentary lifestyle (Lantz et al. 1998), which may be facilitated by stress. Among men (Schnall et al. 1994) and women (Eaker 1998), work

stress has been reported to be a predictor of incident CHD and hypertension (Ironson 1992). However, in women with existing CHD, marital stress is a better predictor of poor prognosis than is work stress (Orth-Gomer et al. 2000).

CONCLUSION

Stress is a central concept for understanding both life and evolution. All creatures face threats to homeostasis, which must be met with adaptive responses. Our future as individuals and as a species depends on our ability to adapt to potent stressors. At a societal level, we face a lack of institutional resources (e.g., inadequate health insurance), pestilence (e.g., HIV/AIDS), war, and international terrorism that has reached our shores. At an individual level, we live with the insecurities of our daily existence including job stress, marital stress, and unsafe schools and neighborhoods. These are not an entirely new condition as, in the last century alone, the world suffered from instances of mass starvation, genocide, revolutions, civil wars, major infectious disease epidemics, two world wars, and a pernicious cold war that threatened the world order. Although we have chosen not to focus on these global threats in this paper, they do provide the backdrop for our consideration of the relationship between stress and health

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